

An EEG-based framework for exploring adaptive rhythmic human-machine interaction

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Abstract:

Objective

Understanding rhythmic human-human interaction and its underlying mechanisms can enhance experiential value and enjoyment by providing a tailored experience and supporting applications in medical human-machine contexts. Existing experimental paradigms often lack a unified and holistic analysis, characterised by limited ecological validity in partner realism, active engagement, and visual interaction. These can produce hidden insights due to variable partner behaviour, inflexible design, or insufficient user experience analysis. The study presents and validates a multimodal paradigm that addresses these limitations and enables controlled evaluation of human-human rhythm interaction and its extension to virtual AI agents.

Approach

Participants completed a tapping paradigm with an audio-visual drum animation driven by either a human or AI-based partner under simple and complex (polyrhythmic) conditions. Portable EEG recordings and post-trial questionnaires assessed neural and subjective responses.

Main results

The framework improves ecological validity relative to existing approaches and effectively masks partner identity (human vs. AI) without reducing experienced flow, arousal, or enjoyment, which remained positive overall. Notably, the AI-based partner considered a first attempt to create a virtual AI-driven interacting drummer, suitable for future consideration of alternative algorithms. Additionally, the design supports unobtrusive, portable EEG measurement of neural modulation and temporal alignment with both performed and presented stimuli.

Significance

This paradigm offers a flexible foundation for studying rhythmic interaction in human-machine systems, balancing ecological realism with experimental partner control while supporting future adaptive or biofeedback-driven systems that optimise rhythm interaction in real-time.

Keywords

EEG, rhythm interaction, adaptive systems, AI, ecological validity

1 Introduction

Rhythm and music naturally guide human behaviour toward synchrony. Whether coordinating with another person or following a beat, the sensation of being “locked” to rhythm is a fundamental component of musical experience [1, 2]. Rhythmic coordination is integral to many aspects of human life, from evolutionary survival [3] to social bonding and emotional connection between individuals [4], and extends

to entertainment, where synchrony enhances musical pleasure [5]. In therapeutic contexts, rhythmic entrainment supports motor recovery after stroke [6], facilitates gait rehabilitation in Parkinson's disease [7], and aids skill development in individuals with autism spectrum disorder [8]. In this work, we approach human-human rhythm interaction as the multimodal coordination between auditory, visual, motor, and affective components during rhythm-centred interaction without strong tonal structure. Thoroughly understanding this interaction is critical for performance, education, and therapeutic applications. Nevertheless, to fully harness its benefits, we require a framework that replicates these real-life components within a controllable, flexible, and analysable context. Paramount, the framework should incorporate tracked embodied engagement, audio-visual coupling between participants and present experience within and between individuals.

Despite extensive work on rhythm perception paradigms, far less is known about how neural entrainment and subjective experience unfold during ecologically valid, interactive rhythmic coordination. Neural paradigms have advanced insights into how humans experience rhythm interaction through the brain's internal representation of rhythm in mainly passive perception paradigms. Using high-density electroencephalography (EEG; typically, 64 channels at 500-16000 Hz), studies have identified neural activity that synchronises with rhythmic auditory stimuli, revealing steady-state evoked potentials (SSEPs) that reflect conscious perception and structuring of musical beat and meter [9]. Similarly, *Nozaradan et al.* [10] demonstrated that neural modulations at meter-related frequencies increase independently of their acoustic prominence, suggesting endogenous neural beat perception to support physical entrainment. These passive paradigms have informed cognitive theories of predictive coding and entrainment in rhythm perception [11], with some work extending into active movement [12, 13]. Beyond rhythm perception, neural approaches have classified emotional experiences in response to music and video using frequency-based and temporal modulation features [14]. Neurological frameworks, emotion or cognition directed, thus further unravel human-rhythm interaction through neural entrainment—the alignment of brain activity with external rhythmic cues—serving as a central tracking mechanism. Nevertheless, with most neural paradigms remaining passive to restrict movement and minimise artefacts, the ecological validity of the evoked experience remains limited [15], with few exceptions [16].

Other paradigms and implementations have integrated a more embodied approach to study human-rhythm interaction, recognising how rhythmic engagement and emotion manifest physically in motion tracking during dancing [17] or how motion may even shape the associated experience [18]. Combining neural and behavioural, hyperscanning paradigms that measure neurological activity across interacting partners. For example, *Lindenberger et al.* [19] used dual 64-channel EEG (5000 Hz) in pairs of performing guitarists and showed that synchronised performers exhibited inter-brain oscillatory coupling, linking shared neural activity to interpersonal coordinated synchrony. Similarly, *Varlet et al.* [20] used dual-EEG (2048 Hz for 64 channels) with 240 Hz motion tracking to examine improvised arm movements, focusing on visual coupling and neural integration of self-other distinctions. Their findings revealed enhanced neural tracking of self-generated movement when leading and of other-generated movements when following. Alternatively, within ensemble performance of pianist duets, [21] (64-channel EEG at 500 Hz), *Washburn et al.* observed synchronisation differences in note onsets and attention-related neural modulations when interacting with a computer participant versus a human partner. These hyperscanning studies explore musical synchrony within shared performance contexts, reflecting an interplay of attention, social, and sensorimotor processes. Other behaviour alternatives, such as facial expressions [22] were considered but not included, due to limited portability and potential masking of less prototypical emotions [23]. Nevertheless, although hyperscanning captures social synchrony in a realistic context, the specificity of the task often limits its applicability to non-proficient individuals.

Both methods, either embodied or passive, are thus constrained in application due to posed proficiency requirements (active) or limitations in the true-to-life character of the interaction (passive). Insight into real-life engaged rhythm creation and the associated neural patterns is thus underdeveloped, limiting the generalisability of findings to broader contexts or audiences. Moreover, human variability also restricts experimental control over the paradigm itself.

Towards accessibility and experimental control, adaptive virtual agents have enabled the emulation of human-like synchrony and helped overcome individual proficiency limitations. *Lauren et al.* [24] employed an adaptive metronome that adjusted its pace in real-time to human asynchronies, improving both single-person and group tapping synchrony. Other research by *Burloiu et al.* [25] created an adaptive drum

agent for musical piece performance that gradually learned human micro-timing drumming nuances, demonstrating the agent's potential to learn more nuanced expressive groove. Such systems enhance understanding of interpersonal interaction by enabling controlled, repeatable, yet realistic paradigms for studying synchrony and engagement. However, application limits emerge for these paradigms as well. Most adaptive agents operating under a synchrony-based optimisation perspective, do not account for the experiential states of the individual, to further enrich their interaction to the human-human equivalent. Hence, the need for neural-based experience identification is reintroduced.

Collectively, understanding real-life human-music/rhythm interaction thus requires an integrated framework that encompasses behavioural alignment, emotional engagement, cognitive representations, and importantly, predictive mechanisms to drive alignment and synchrony [2, 3, 4, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30]. A unified approach can overcome trade-offs between realism and control, with passive EEG paradigms offering high spatial resolution at the cost of physical engagement [10, 14, 15, 31, 32], while active hyperscanning studies lack control and generalisability. Moreover, adaptive agents could offer a human-like, generalisable middle ground [24, 33], where experience tracking may guide future neuro-adaptive steering to further improve musical interaction [34, 35].

From this envisioned true-to-life paradigm, defined by control and equivalence in experience and behaviour between a virtual and human partner, we posed two aims within our paradigm to validate its ability to replicate a human-like experience with a virtual agent, while capturing neural dynamics in a reduced montage:

1. **Can an adaptive virtual agent evoke comparable synchrony and subjective experience during rhythmic interaction to a human partner?**

Building on the framework's adaptive agent and avatar masking, we expect to obtain similar physical and subjective experiences across human and virtual agent conditions.

2. **Can a low-density, mobile EEG montage accurately capture neural markers of task-related modulations of rhythmic interaction, consistent with prior high-density EEG findings**

Using literature-based electrode selection [12, 16, 36], a localised low-density electrode montage was evaluated to capture rhythm-related neural modulations, mirroring those observed in 64-channel setups with condition-dependent spectral changes.

A portable audio-visual hyperscanning system was developed to enable real-time behavioural and neural monitoring during a two-person tapping task with either a human or an adaptive virtual AI partner. During interaction, the partner is represented by an animated avatar to provide a controllable yet realistic audio-visual rhythmic interaction. A portable low-density montage captured neural recordings simultaneously. This design aimed to mask the partner's origin (human or AI) and is readily extendable to other interactive paradigms, thereby driving future research.

Novelty of our approach lies in integrating an adaptive virtual AI agent and animated avatar into a portable EEG framework, thereby extending the ecological validity of standardised neural research through a more realistic active design. Through its experimental control, it broadens the application complex paradigms to diverse participant groups. In essence, the system enables real-time multimodal analysis of rhythmic interaction, effectively balancing experiment control and realism. In addition, the paradigm established a foundation for future EEG-driven closed-loop adaptation, where a virtual AI partner could dynamically optimise the user experience in real-time.

2 Methods

2.1 System

To allow the in-depth evaluation of both set-out objectives of matching behaviour synchrony and experience with a virtual AI agent, as well as allowing low-density EEG capture of task-related neural modulations, an interactive rhythmic paradigm was designed. Within the remainder of this paper, the wording of *AI* and *virtual AI partner/agent* was used interchangeably to denote the artificial computer-controlled agent.

The framework implements an audio-visual tapping synchronisation task with a rhythmic partner. Participants are seated in two separate rooms in front of a computer screen and fitted with an EEG electrode montage (Figure 1). This setup builds upon earlier in-house research on neural markers of human-rhythm interaction, extending the original experiment into a multimodal (audio-visual) paradigm [16], in which the system was designed to support ecological validity, portability and future neuro-adaptive closed-loop applications capable of adjusting experience based on real-time neural states. Experiments were conducted in the Extended Realities and Human Interactions Labs (XRHIL) of Ghent University [37].

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the setup and signal flows for an interaction where both participants interact with their respective virtual AI agent. Devices (white) are managed by the central control over OSC as indicated with a grey bar. Lines represent needed information flows including tapping data (yellow), visual information (green), auditory streams (blue), and EEG-data streams (grey).

Auditory-visual presentation and neural-behavioural recordings are managed by a network of seven computing units: two dedicated virtual AI agents for the human-machine interactions (AI 1 & 2), two laptops for displaying instructional prompts and audio-visual content through Unity [38] (UNITY 1 & 2), two in-house designed EEG-recording devices (EEG 1 & 2) and one central control computer that manages

synchronised playback across all components (CENTRAL CONTROL), Figure 1. Communication between devices occurs over OSC (barred lines), where a Rosendahl Nanosync clock generator, operating at 120 Hz, aligns stimulus presentation, EEG recordings, and the produced taps and beats.

The central control manages auditory routing, visual presentation, and condition-based prompting, as well as general recording of incoming tapping data and EEG responses through MAX/MSP [39] over OSC. Audio routing ensures participants only heard the audio of their current rhythmic partner (AI vs human), combined with guiding beats. The audio stimuli are delivered via the Dante audio protocol at 44.1 kHz (256-sample buffer) [40], based on detected onsets from tapping pad pressure values or discrete AI input. EMF radiation-free earbuds are used for stimulus playback [41]. Partner beats are rendered in MAX/MSP using low-frequency drum samples, while high-pitched tones represent guiding beats. Taps are recorded using custom-designed drum pads with pressure-sensitive scales connected to Bela Mini boards [42]. Both scales stream real-time pressure values via OSC to MAX/MSP (latency: 1 ms, sample rate: 22.05 kHz,[42, 43]), Figure 2.

Figure 2: Illustration of the in-house EEG recording device with 8-channel electrode montage (left) and the used pressure-sensitive scales, which were converted to OSC streams using Bela mini board (right)

2.1.1 Neural activity

EEG devices are designed for real-time on-device logging and data analysis, as well as external control and data transmission over OSC (24-bit, 16 kHz, Figure 2) [44, 45]. Both devices run on battery power

Figure 3: Electrode placement on a participant (left) and associated electrode selection overlaid on the averaged motor localiser from *Van Ransbeeck et al.[16]*. Dot colour indicates selection origin between motor (green) or experience(red)

to minimise grid noise, while an Ethernet cable ensures reliable data transmission and alignment. Signals are recorded at 500 Hz from eight passive electrode locations (P3, PO3, AFz, F2, T7, FT7, T8, and FT8) with impedances kept below $10\text{ k}\Omega$ through abrasive gel and skin preparation.

The limited channel selection, compared to conventional 32/64-channel montages, is motivated by the envisioned framework's need for high portability and flexibility in future active paradigms. The aimed real-time data access and portable context required a limited channel count to reduce overall device dimensions. The eight recorded electrode sites are split between emotion-related areas (T7, FT7, T8, FT8), optimal for emotion classification [46], and motor-related regions (P3, PO3, AFz, F2) associated with neural modulation [12, 47]. The motor-related selection is additionally informed by in-house research [16] on localised motor activity within independent components.

Channel selection from the independent component weightings prioritises electrodes with the highest contribution to motor activity, including those with the most negative (AFz, F2) and positive (P3, PO3) weights(Figure 3). Motor-related electrodes are mirrored for left-handed participants (P4, PO4, AFz, F1, T7, FT7, T8, FT8).

2.1.2 Visual presentation

Visual stimuli are managed in separate Unity instances for each participant and presented on a 23.8-inch screen (60 Hz) positioned 80 cm from the participant, with a central fixation cross at eye level. To provide visual feedback on the participant's performance, the cross's luminance is gradually adjusted throughout the interaction to reflect synchrony [16]. In Unity, luminance is scaled between 0 (poor synchrony) and 1 (good synchrony) by modifying the emission colour value of the cross object. On each frame, performance is evaluated based on the alignment of the user-generated and heard taps. If synchrony is adequate, emission scaling increased in steps of 0.0016 per frame to a maximum of 1, producing slow variations perceptible over several seconds and avoiding sudden visual artefacts. Conversely, poor synchrony reduces scaling at the same rate to a minimum of 0 (transparent). Although avatar animations compete for visual attention, participants are instructed to maintain their gaze on the cross. Hence, to minimise distraction and eye movement artefacts, performance feedback is limited to the cross, while the avatar serves to enhance realism and visual support. This dual visual input mirrors previous integration tasks of a fixation cross with other variable stimuli to maintain attention in interpersonal synchrony [18] or within neurological research on short visual events [48].

Avatar animations are rendered in Unity [38] separately for each participant using two overlapped looped sequences. A continuously drumming avatar follows the partner's beats, while an overlaid moving sphere indicates the task to perform. White spheres followed a circular path (right to left) on the screen and were time-aligned to pass the central fixation cross at the required tapping instances for both participants, indicating their individual task. Sphere guidance is limited to the initial 32 seconds of each trial. To enhance realism, full-body motion capture of a playing drummer [49] is mapped onto a stick-figure manikin (left side, Figure 4). Avatar timing is governed by a Kuramoto model to align visual animations with auditory beats from the rhythmic partner (AI or human). The abstraction to an intermediate shared avatar helps to conceal partner identity and increases interaction realism compared to auditory-only paradigms [50].

Figure 4: Excerpts of the visual illustrations for the participants. *Left*: Schematic illustration of a $[2 : 3]$ condition depicted prior to the interaction, showing the first-beat metronome (white), ternary task rhythm (yellow), and binary reference beat (blue). *Right*: Visual support during the 32-second lead-in of an interaction, showing a guiding white sphere for initial tapping and an animated stick-figure following the partner's input.

2.1.3 Virtual AI Agent

The virtual AI agent is implemented as a real-time reservoir computing network [51]. This model was chosen for its similarities to neural functioning and its demonstrated ability to accurately perceive, predict, and adapt to rhythmic patterns [51], potentially enabling human-like interactions. The model produces continuous output, which is transformed into beat onsets using peak detection above a predefined threshold. During each virtual AI agent trial, each participant is then paired with a separate instance of the adaptive model, with pre-trained versions for each condition and task. Biological plausibility of the underlying AI model is achieved by requiring the virtual AI agent to be predictive rather than reactive. This represents a biological system that must trigger a motor action before execution due to the intrinsic latency of the auditory system. In global, this is represented by the agent's prediction horizon of 200 ms and associated temporal resolution of 6 ms. To respond to its human counterpart, the model observes its taps and combines this information with its own target derived from the initial visual cues.

In addition, a learning rate (LR) parameter modulates adaptability, allowing the model to be more ($LR = 1$) or less ($LR = 0$) adaptive to its partner to achieve synchronisation (default $LR = 0.5$). In the current study, LR was fixed at 0.5, although it opens up future research opportunities for real-time adaptation based on external metrics. Two high-performance servers (Intel Xeon Gold 6136, 128 GB RAM, NVIDIA GeForce 2080Ti) manage the real-time model calculations for virtual AI agents' predictions and execution.

2.2 Evaluation task

The framework was validated by analysing participants' subjective experience, behavioural synchrony, and neural activity during human-human and human-machine interactions. User responses were used to assess how synchrony and experience varied by partner type, addressing the goal of establishing an equivalent experience across interactions (Target One). In parallel, a reduced EEG montage was evaluated by comparing neural signatures against in-house datasets and related literature to confirm the presence of expected spectral patterns and condition-dependent modulations (Target Two).

The interaction paradigms were adapted from *Van Kerrebroeck et al.* [52], who examined an audio-visual rhythmic interaction with a human- or computer-controlled avatar. Our study extends this work in three ways. First, a masked design ensured an indistinguishable experience of both partner types, increasing control and reproducibility. Second, the integration of a portable neural recording device enabled real-time access to neural patterns, forming the basis for future neuro-adaptive applications. Third, the abstraction of participant taps into a standardised drum animation increased ecological validity while maintaining accessibility for individuals with limited mobility.

During each trial, participants performed either a binary or a ternary rhythm together with a partner, which could be another human (**HP**) or a pre-trained model (**AI**) capable of performing both simple and complex (polyrhythmic) conditions [51]. The presence of a virtual AI partner was not disclosed to the participants. To maintain engagement and balance skill and challenge, conditions were varied in difficulty:

- *Simple* matched interactions, in which both participants performed the same rhythm, either binary-binary [2 : 2] or ternary-ternary [3 : 3]
- *Complex* conditions, involving complementary rhythms, binary-ternary [2 : 3] or ternary-binary [3 : 2], see Figure 4).

Eight conditions were evaluated, defined by the combination of performed rhythm and heard partner rhythm (Table 1), with audio routing determining the heard partner. Two additional conditions ([3 : 3]

AI and [3 : 3] HP) were included for future test-retest analysis. The ten total conditions were presented in randomised order to avoid possible fixed-order effects.

Condition Room 1	Task		Sound Room 1	Task		Sound Room 2
	HP 1	AI 1		HP 2	AI 2	
[2 : 2]	Binary	\	HP 2	Binary	\	HP 1
[3 : 3]	Ternary	\	HP 2	Ternary	\	HP 1
[2 : 3]	Ternary	\	HP 2	Binary	\	HP 1
[3 : 2]	Binary	\	HP 2	Ternary	\	HP 1
[2 : 2]	Binary	Binary	AI 2	Binary	Binary	AI 1
[3 : 3]	Ternary	Ternary	AI 2	Ternary	Ternary	AI 1
[2 : 3]	Ternary	Ternary	AI 2	Binary	Binary	AI 1
[3 : 2]	Binary	Binary	AI 2	Ternary	Ternary	AI 1
[3 : 3] retest	Ternary	\	HP 2	Ternary	\	HP 1
[3 : 3] retest	Ternary	Ternary	AI 2	Ternary	Ternary	AI 1

Table 1: Overview of conditions relative to room 1, varying tasks and heard rhythms. Condition notation reflects the heard rhythm followed by the performed rhythm. *Task* columns show the required rhythms from the virtual AI agents (AI 1, AI 2) and human participants (HP 1 and HP 2). *Sound* columns indicate the partner heard in each room.

In the polyrhythmic conditions, both human participants performed different rhythms. For example, in a [2 : 3] condition from room 1's perspective, the participant performed a ternary task while hearing the partner's binary task. From room 2's perspective, the same physical interaction appears as a [3 : 2] condition, executing a binary rhythm while hearing their partner's ternary rhythm. Throughout the manuscript, conditions are referenced using a general notation without their frame of reference, in which the first index denotes the heard rhythm and the second index the performed rhythm.

Binary and ternary tapping rates were based on a repeating six-beat metronome at 3.75 Hz, resulting in binary taps at 1.25 Hz (0.8 s) and ternary taps at 1.875 Hz (0.566 s). These frequencies fall within the general range of musical tempo (40 bpm-240 bpm) [53] and relate to the spontaneous tempo for tapping and dancing around 2 Hz (120 bpm) [54]. The exact frequencies were provided only during the initial audio-visual illustration and lead-in phase of each trial. Afterwards, a natural drift in frequencies was expected. Participants were instructed to maintain good, shared performance, even if this required adjusting their pace to continue the underlying shared rhythmic pattern.

2.2.1 Trial timeline

Each trial consisted of four phases (Figure 5)

1) **Initial Instructions** (30 s): A visual prompt introduced the required rhythm and instructed participants to sit comfortably and relax their muscles, while limiting movement to the tapping hand and finger. Participants were asked to maintain fixation on a central cross in the middle of the screen while being allowed to blink.

2) **Audio-Visual Illustration** (22.4 s): A colour-coded visual illustration depicted the condition and its metrical structure (metronome, task rhythm, heard rhythm), accompanied by an audio cue reflecting the same pattern (Figure 4).

3) **Interaction Phase** (90 s (training) or 192 s (main)): Participants engaged in a tapping interaction with their rhythmic partner (human or AI), supported by auditory partner feedback and synchronised avatar animation. A 32-second lead-in with an oscillating sphere guided initial tapping. (See *Supplementary Material 1* for an animated example). Throughout the interaction, the fixation cross gradually changed in luminance to reflect performance quality [16].

4) **Post-Trial Questionnaire**: Participants rated their experience immediately after each trial.

Before the main trials, participants completed shortened 90-second training versions of the interaction phase using only human-human interactions. This familiarised participants with the setup and reduced learning effects.

Each condition was practised up to three times, depending on the participant's preference. Training conditions were presented in a fixed order, within room 1 following ([2 : 2], [2 : 3], [3 : 2], and [3 : 3]) and room 2 following ([2 : 2], [3 : 2], [2 : 3], and [3 : 3]) to support engagement and balanced progressions from simple to more demanding rhythms.

Figure 5: Timeline of training and main experiment trials. Training interactions lasted 90 seconds instead of 192 seconds.

2.2.2 Post-trial questionnaire

After each main trial, both participants completed a questionnaire assessing perceived agency and shared agency [52], self-other integration (SOI) [55], and flow. Flow was measured using five items from the Flow Short Scale, covering *fluency of performance* and *absorption by activity* [56] (Supplementary Material 2). The items were summed to construct a composite flow score (range 5-35), though internal consistency in the study was modest (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.63$). Emotional pleasure and arousal were measured using the Affective Slider [57]. System validation analyses focused on pleasure, arousal, and flow.

2.3 Participants

Thirty participants (16 females and 14 males) took part in the study and registered in pairs with their rhythmic partner, ensuring prior familiarity. Participants were aged between 19 and 31 years ($M = 25$, $SD = 3$). All participants provided written informed consent after receiving information on the nature of the experiment. Ethical approval was granted by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Arts and Philosophy on the 7th of January 2025 [2024-71], and all procedures adhered to the Declaration of

Helsinki.

Prior to the experiment, participants provided medical, musical, and educational background information to allow for potential subject-level corrections in future analyses. However, these factors were not examined in depth in the present study, as the primary focus was system and paradigm validation rather than individual differences. Hearing ability was screened as well using an on-site digits-in-noise test of the WHO (hearWHO, [58]) with over-ear headphones. Individual scores above 70 were considered sufficient, and results ranged from 70 to 90. One participant scored 60 and was excluded from further analysis. Seventeen participants reported caffeine intake prior to the experiment.

Musical proficiency was assessed using the Musical Training subscale of the Goldsmiths Musical Sophistication Index [59], with scores ranging from 6 to 46 ($M = 26.6$, $SD = 11.8$). Participants' highest completed education ranged from high school diplomas to master's degrees. Twenty-nine participants reported being right-handed, and one reported being left-handed.

Participants were pre-screened via an online or in-person interview to assess rhythmic proficiency. During the session, participants were informed about the experimental requirements, including simple and complex interactions with their rhythmic partner. Rhythmic abilities were screened using three tasks. 1) **Metronome continuation task:** Participants synchronised taps with an online auditory metronome and continued tapping after the metronome faded [60]. A score was returned after completing the continuation. The task could be completed twice, with the best score retained. A cutoff score of 500 (maximum 1000) was required, corresponding to a maximum mean offset of 25 ms per tap relative to the beat. 2) **Polyrhythm synchronisation task:** Participants synchronised claps or taps with either the binary or ternary component of a video clip showing a [2 : 3] polyrhythm of two bouncing balls with corresponding sounds [61]. Performance was assessed based on the ability to maintain the rhythm without relying on visual cues. 3) **Polyrhythm continuation task:** Participants synchronised with either the binary or ternary component of a looped [2 : 3] or [3 : 2] auditory polyrhythm [62, 63]. In the second half of the stimulus, their target rhythm was no longer present, requiring internally maintained continuation synchronised to the complementary audio.

The latter two tasks were untimed and primarily served as orientation and familiarisation tools. After some practice and verbal feedback, all participants were judged able to maintain and continue the required rhythms and were therefore included in the study.

2.4 Analysis

Analysis was conducted in *Python 3.11.5* using the packages *numpy* and *pandas*, with *matplotlib* and *seaborn* for visualisation and *scipy* for statistical analysis. Behavioural synchrony metrics and neural features were analysed to identify equivalence between human-human and human-machine interactions and to assess the suitability of a reduced electrode montage for capturing task-related neural modulation.

Given the symmetrical experimental setup, features were calculated from two separate executing reference frames. For each participant, neural activity and tapping data T_n were analysed relative to the external partner beat rhythm B_n , referred to as the reference beat. In human-human interactions, this required switching the task and reference signals between analyses of each participant, such that T_n and B_n were interchanged accordingly. Accordingly, the questionnaire responses of both participants were considered within their respective reference frame throughout the interactions. Moreover, to provide a meticulous analysis of the present equivalence in user experience and the suitability of low-density EEG, the analysis pipeline was split into two separate contexts to validate both components. User responses, detailing the physical alignment and user experience of the interactions, followed by EEG-processing detailing task-related neural modulations linked to perceived and performed rhythms.

2.4.1 User responses

To evaluate similarity in behavioural and experiential responses between AI and human interactions, behavioural synchrony and user experience were compared between both partner types, where similarity in responses is considered a supporting argument for the effective masking of interaction partner to a comparable experience.

Figure 6: Processing pipeline for calculation of the resultant vector length R from user input taps T_n and heard beats B_n (left), along with an in-depth illustration of theoretical beat construction B_n^* from perceived beats B_n for a $[2 : 3]$ interaction.

Behavioural synchrony metrics were derived from participants' tap onsets (T_n) relative to the heard partner beat onsets (B_n) in the full 192-second interaction, where each n denotes an individual event. Heard beats B_n originated from either the human partner or the virtual AI agent. Redundant beat detections occurring within 200 ms of a previous event were removed.

The resultant vector length (R) was used as a circular measure of phase alignment between executed taps and reference beats [64, 65]. However, because computation of R assumes comparable tap and beat frequencies, a theoretical beat signal B_n^* was constructed - primarily for polyrhythmic conditions - to represent the ideal tap timings required for perfect synchrony with the heard beat signal (B_n), irrespective of the executed task [16] (Figure 6).

This construction involved segmenting beats B_n into equal-duration subdivisions to form an underlying six-beat cycle (Figure 6), consisting of three equal subdivisions for binary rhythms and two for ternary

rhythms. The theoretical beat signal B_n^* was then obtained by regrouping this six-beat structure according to the required task of the analysed participant. For simple conditions, $B_n^* = B_n$.

From these theoretical beats, resultant vector lengths R were computed via relative phase angles ϕ_n , quantifying timing differences between an executed tap T_n , its nearest theoretical reference beat B_n^* , and the subsequent beat B_{n+1}^* (Equation 1). Positive phase values indicate delayed taps, whereas negative values indicate a leading tap:

$$\phi_n = 2\pi \left(\frac{T_n - B_n^*}{B_{(n+1)}^* - B_n^*} \right) \quad (1)$$

Resultant vector lengths were computed using equation 2 (*pycircstat.resultant_vector_length*,[66]) over the full 192-second interaction and served as the primary synchrony metric. Here, N denotes the total number of executed taps, and R values range from 0 (no synchrony) to 1 (perfect synchrony).

$$R = \left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \exp(i\phi_n) \right| \quad (2)$$

Notably, this construction assumes initial alignment of the first beat B_0 as illustrated in the example, Figure 6. In complex interactions, perceptual ambiguity or execution error may introduce fixed phase offsets. When present from the start of an interaction, such constant offsets do not affect R , as the measure is invariant to a constant phase shift. However, missed or skipped beats during the interaction introduce additional phase discontinuities, potentially shifting taps by $\pm 60^\circ$ relative to the original theoretical reference.

Post-hoc analysis of averaged resultant vector lengths R_i computed over non-overlapping 32-second windows revealed a median ratio of 96% ($IQR = 14\%$) relative to full window R measurements for simple conditions, decreasing to 75% ($IQR = 50\%$) for complex conditions. Beyond the expected reduction in phase consistency (R) when analysing shorter windows, complex conditions show an additional decrease attributed to reference misalignment due to human error. Consequently, resultant vector lengths were

handled with caution, particularly for polyrhythmic interactions.

To assess the effect of partner type on behavioural synchrony and subjective experience (flow, pleasure, and arousal), condition-dependent modulation was analysed using linear mixed-effects models (*statsmodels.formula.api*). Partner type (human vs. AI) and task complexity (simple vs. complex), along with their interaction, were included as fixed effects, while participant was included as a random intercept. Effective masking of partner identity was validated by the absence of significant partner-related effects. Where significant effects were observed, robustness was further assessed using post-hoc Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (*scipy.stat*, two-sided).

2.4.2 EEG-processing

EEG data processing followed procedures established in prior work [16] to validate the reproducibility of task-related neural modulation within a reduced-electrode montage by constructing similar motor-based features. The initial 32 seconds of each recording (lead-in) were discarded to limit contamination from additional audio-visual cueing, leaving only the unbiased interaction period. An overview of the neural processing pipelines is shown in Figure 7

Signals were band-pass filtered between 0.1 Hz and 250 Hz (*scipy.signal.lfilter*) using a type-I finite impulse response (FIR) (*scipy.signal.firwin*; *numtaps* = 8251, *band* = [0.1,249], *pass_zero* = *False*, *window* = 'hamming'), with correction for group delay. This frequency range removed low-frequency drift while preserving all task-relevant frequencies of the rhythmic interactions, including those aligned with the six-beat periodicity (0.625 Hz, [12]). Two additional FIR notch filters were applied at 50 Hz and 100 Hz to suppress power-line noise (*scipy.signal.firwin*; *numtaps* = 1001, *band* = [48-52] [98-102], *pass_zero* = *False*, *window* = 'hamming'), followed by corresponding time-shift corrections.

Within the filtered signals, poor-quality measurements were identified by visual inspection of individual channel trajectories for unstable and saturated values and were excluded from further analysis. In total, 28 recordings were removed from the initial set of 290 measurements (29 participants). The remaining data were referenced to a four-channel average (T7, FT7, T8, F8) to maintain a symmetrical reference.

Figure 7: Processing pipeline for motor-based neural modulations analysis of peak magnitudes.

To account for natural drift in tapping rates during unguided interaction, EEG channels were time-warped based on perceived partner beat onsets B_n , matching inter-beat intervals to the original guidance period [67]. This procedure enabled analysis of drifting neural modulation patterns while preserving beat alignment.

The referenced EEG data were epoched relative to perceived beat onsets (B_n). Epochs exceeding 1.5 seconds were removed, reflecting likely omission of at least a single tap under an assumed minimum tapping rate of approximately 1 Hz (60 bpm). Epochs containing eye-blinks or movement artefacts were rejected using a maximum admissible voltage step of 50 mV. On average, a total of 235 epochs ($SD = 19$) remained per interaction for binary audio conditions ($[2 : 2], [2 : 3]$) and 354 epochs ($SD = 16$) for the ternary audio conditions ($[3 : 3], [3 : 2]$).

Remaining epochs were time-warped by linearly interpolating the variable epoch lengths to match the originally imposed beat intervals: 0.800 s (400 samples) for binary conditions and 0.566 s (267 samples) for the ternary conditions (*numpy.interp*). Warped segments were concatenated and trimmed to multiples of 3.2 seconds (two six-beat measures) to allow peak analysis at task- and beat-related frequencies with minimal spectral leakage. The used 3.2-second window comprised either 1600 or 1602 samples, depending on the beat stretching. Binary interactions ($[2 : 2], [2 : 3]$) spanned on average 156.6 s ($SD = 18.6$ s) for human-human interactions and 153.8 s ($SD = 5.6$ s) for human-machine interactions. For ternary heard beats ($[3 : 3], [3 : 2]$), stretched human-human interactions spanned 159.1 s ($SD = 10.3$ s), and

human-machine interactions 152.1 s ($SD = 9.0$ s).

Given the limited scalp coverage, neural modulation analysis focused exclusively on motor-centred components, despite the relevance of auditory regions for rhythm processing [12, 16, 68]. Motor components were derived from localised sensorimotor activation patterns identified in previous high-density EEG research [16]. Due to the restricted electrode count, independent component analysis was not applied. Alternatively, motor-related components were reconstructed by redistributing and summing localised independent component weights from a 64-channel motor localiser to the nearest available electrodes (P3, PO3, and F2), following established channel-reduction strategies [47]. Although similar contributions were observed in the AFz electrode relative to the other three, this electrode was excluded because improved modulation clarity was achieved when using only three channels. After subtracting the mean electrode weight from the three electrodes to enforce reference independence, weights were normalised to sum to unity. The resulting weights (P3: 0.261, PO3: 0.239, F2: -0.500) were applied to the stretched EEG data to derive motor-related modulation signals (MOT ICs) for each participant and condition.

Neural task-related modulations were analysed in the frequency domain using a discrete Fourier transform (DFT; [69], *scipy.fft.fft*). Task-related activity was separated from background noise by subtracting a noise estimate derived from neighbouring frequency bands in the magnitude spectrum of the motor signals [36, 67]. Noise estimates were computed by averaging spectral magnitudes from the 6th to 15th sidebands on both sides of each target frequency, assuming local spectral noise similarity in the absence of steady-state evoked potentials.

Cleaned magnitude spectra of the motor component were evaluated at 12 frequencies evenly spaced at 0.3125 Hz, starting from 0.625 Hz. This selection included the executed task frequencies (1.25 Hz for binary rhythms and 1.875 Hz for ternary rhythms), prominent harmonics (2.5 Hz and 3.75), and the six-beat guidance measure frequency (0.625 Hz). Seven additional task-unrelated frequencies were included to assess the specificity of task-related modulation. However, since spectral peaks were slightly shifted due to interpolation-based time warping (1600 vs 1604 samples), denoised peak magnitudes were estimated by selecting the maximum value across the three frequency bins closest to each target

frequency [10, 70]. Magnitudes at each of the 12 frequencies were evaluated against zero using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (*scipy.stat*, two-sided) for both human and AI interactions separately. Three additional mixed-effect models assessed the impact of condition and partner type, along with their interaction term, on modulation strength at the main task-related frequencies of 0.625 Hz, 1.25 Hz, and 1.875 Hz. A random participant intercept was also included.

Notably, although achievable, alternative hyperscanning metrics such as phase-locking values and frequency coupling were not included. While such measures could reveal valuable shared neural dynamics during human-human interaction, their application is restricted in human-machine contexts due to the absence of neural signals in the virtual AI agent. Moreover, the present analysis prioritised task-centred neural signals within individuals rather than between subjects.

2.4.3 Statistical corrections

To control for multiple comparisons in the setup tests, Holm-Bonferroni corrections were applied to reported p-values, providing family-wise error-controlled significance estimates. Corrections were applied to the Wilcoxon signed-rank tests for the assessment of 1) Post-hoc task-complexity effects across behavioural and experiential metrics (4 metrics), 2) Post-hoc partner-type effects with controlling for task-complexity (8 tests; 4 metrics in two complexities), and 3) Neural peak significance assessment within each condition (12 frequencies). Additionally, corrections were applied to the assessment of condition and partner-type effects at task-related peaks in the mixed-effect models (3 frequencies).

3 Results

3.1 Experience and synchronisation

To evaluate whether the system can support ecologically valid and engaging interactions equivalent to human-human exchange within a controlled framework, we analysed behavioural performance and sub-

jective experience across both human-human (HP) and human-machine (AI) interactions. The analysis examined condition- and partner-related effects on emotional responses and physical synchronisation. Linear mixed-effect models were fitted for each outcome variable, with partner type, task complexity, and their interaction as fixed effects and participant random intercept. Interactions were classified as simple matched conditions ($[2 : 2], [3 : 3]$), where participants performed the same task or complex polyrhythmic conditions ($[2 : 3], [3 : 2]$), in which participants performed complementary tasks. The four dependent measures - behavioural synchrony R , arousal, flow, and pleasure - were modelled separately. All models converged successfully, with Log-likelihood of 2.8 (synchrony), -923.7 (arousal), -602.6 (flow), and -932.2 (pleasure) (Appendix A). Residuals were approximately normally distributed, random-intercept variances were positive, and homoscedasticity across participants was confirmed for all measures except synchrony R (White tests, $p < 0.001$), which was therefore interpreted with caution.

Across models, task complexity significantly modulated behavioural synchrony, arousal, and pleasure. Synchrony was markedly higher in simple than in complex conditions ($\beta = -0.40$, $SE = 0.04$, $t(213) = -9.40$, $p < 0.001$), indicating greater temporal alignment under matched rhythmic context. Complexity also increased arousal ($\beta = 7.08$, $SE = 3.29$, $t(213) = 2.15$, $p = 0.031$) and decreased pleasure ($\beta = -7.17$, $SE = 3.55$, $t(213) = -2.02$, $p = 0.043$), suggesting elevated arousal and reduced enjoyment during polyrhythmic interaction (Figure 9). No significant main effects of partner type or interaction effects were observed for any model.

Robustness of complexity effects was further evaluated using post-hoc Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (two-sided), with scores averaged per participant across partner types. After Holm-Bonferroni correction, complexity effects remained significant only for behavioural synchrony R ($p_{corr} < 0.001$, $W = 1142$) and were absent for flow, pleasure, and arousal ($p_{corr} > 0.050$). These findings indicate that task complexity primarily impacts temporal alignment, largely indifferent to the interaction partner.

Accounting for the dominant influence of task complexity, partner effects were reassessed while controlling for complexity. Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (two-sided, averaged per participant and complexity) revealed no significant differences between human and AI interaction in flow and arousal. Pleasure ratings were

Figure 8: Complexity and partner effects by mixed-effect models for simple ($[2 : 2]$, $[3 : 3]$) and complex ($[2 : 3]$, $[3 : 2]$) interactions within human-human (HP) and human-machine (AI) conditions. Outcome measures included flow, pleasure, arousal, and behavioural synchrony (R) and were averaged per participant, partner type and complexity for illustration. Asterisks indicate significance levels ($p < .001$ (***) , $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < 0.05$ (*)).

higher for virtual AI partners in both simple ($W = 112.5$, $p = 0.039$) and complex ($W = 116.0$, $p = 0.048$) conditions. Similarly, humans appeared to synchronise better with the virtual AI agents than with their human partner ($W = 99.0$, $p = 0.017$). Further post-hoc comparison within simple interactions by a Wilcoxon signed-rank test of the interbeat intervals ($B_n^* - B_{n-1}^*$, two-sided, averaged per participant) similarly suggested a clear difference in inter-beat standard deviation between human and AI-based partners. However, none of the main partner-related effects survived Holm-Bonferroni correction across the eight comparisons (4 markers \times 2 complexities, $\alpha = 0.05$), suggesting a general invariance of a participant's experience and behaviour to partner type and indicating the targeted equivalence in the user sensation.

3.1.1 Neural entrainment features

To evaluate whether the reduced electrode montage reliably captured task-related neural dynamics, neural activity was analysed using frequency-based motor modulation features and compared against established findings in the literature. Successful replication of known rhythmic entrainment patterns and condition-dependent modulation was taken as evidence of correct system functioning. Test-retest measurements were excluded from this analysis.

Furthermore, only interactions exhibiting reliable behavioural synchrony were retained, defined by a

significant Rayleigh test ($p < 0.05$) and a conservative synchrony threshold of ($R > 0.5$). This criterion was inspired by reported transitions between phase-coherent and incoherent gait patterns [71] (Appendix B).

For simple trials ($[2 : 2]$ and $[3 : 3]$), Resultant vector lengths attained a median value of 0.88 ($IQR = 0.20$) where 99% of trials passed the synchrony criterion ($R > 0.5$ & Rayleigh test). Complex trials ($[2 : 3]$, $[3 : 2]$) synchronised less with a median R of 0.31 ($IQR = 0.65$) and only 38% passing the criterion. After selection, the remaining dataset comprised 52 $[2 : 2]$, 54 $[3 : 3]$, 22 $[2 : 3]$, and 19 $[3 : 2]$ interactions (see Appendix C for details).

For the retained measurements, Figure 9 presents normalised motor spectra, highlighting neural modulations to the presented rhythmic structure. Across all conditions, significant spectral peaks emerged at task-related and beat-related frequencies and their harmonics (2.5 Hz and 3.75 Hz ($p < .05$)), indicating robust neural activity in both simple and complex conditions. As expected, peaks were absent at frequencies that were not integer multiples of the six-beat measure (0.625 Hz). However, isolated task-unrelated peaks did appear, such as 1.875 Hz in the $[2 : 2]$ condition and 1.25 Hz and 2.5 Hz in the $[3 : 3]$ condition. Notably, the shared sub-harmonic at 0.625 Hz, reflecting the global six-beat cycle, was consistently significant across all conditions.

Condition- ($[2 : 2]$, $[3 : 3]$, $[2 : 3]$, $[3 : 2]$) and partner-based (AI vs. HP) effects, as well as their interaction, were further examined using separate mixed-effect models for peak amplitudes at 1.25 Hz, 1.875 Hz and their shared subharmonic (0.625 Hz). Models converged with Log-likelihood of -32.5, 14.4 and -58.5, respectively. Residuals showed no clear visual deviation from normality, although heteroscedasticity was detected for the 1.25 Hz model (White test, $p < 0.05$) and results for this frequency were therefore interpreted cautiously.

After Holm-Bonferroni correction, significant condition-dependent modulations were observed at both task and beat frequencies. For the 1.25 Hz peak, amplitudes differed significantly from the $[2 : 2]$ baseline in $[2 : 3]$ ($\beta = -0.24$, $SE = 0.10$, $t(146) = -2.42$, $p_{corr} = 0.032$) and $[3 : 3]$ ($\beta = -0.40$, $SE = 0.07$, $t(146) = -5.64$, $p_{corr} = 0.003$). For the ternary rhythm, 1.875 Hz amplitudes were significantly

modulated in $[2 : 3]$ ($\beta = 0.26$, $SE = 0.81$, $t(146) = 3.22$, $p_{corr} = 0.001$), $[3 : 2]$ ($\beta = 0.34$, $SE = 0.09$, $t(146) = 3.73$, $p_{corr} = 0.001$) and $[3 : 3]$ ($\beta = 0.44$, $SE = 0.06$, $t(146) = 7.67$, $p = 0.001$)

No significant condition-related effects were observed for the shared subharmonic (0.625 Hz) after correction for the three models, and no effects of partner-type were detected at any of our three frequencies ($p_{corr} > 0.05$).

We acknowledge that restricting analysis to synchronised trials may bias peak amplitudes and inflate significance. However, post-hoc analysis without synchrony-based selection yielded comparable task-related peaks and condition effects while also revealing no partner-related differences, supporting the robustness of the observed neural entrainment patterns. Independent of synchrony, these neural findings as a whole suggest clear identification of task- and beat-related modulation, supporting further evaluation of their similarity to literature.

Figure 9: Normalised motor-localised spectra (DFT) for synchronised human-human (HP) and human-machine (AI) interactions ($R > 0.5$). Panel titles indicate conditions and corresponding beat (B) and task (T) frequencies. Legends report the number of synchronised interactions relative to the total number of trials per partner type. One $[3 : 2]$ outlier fell outside the plotted range. Peak significance was assessed at 12 frequencies using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm-Bonferroni correction ($p_{corr} < .001$ (***) , $.001 < p_{corr} < 0.01$ (**), $.01 < p_{corr} < 0.05$ (*))

4 Discussion

This study introduces a multimodal framework for investigating human-rhythm interaction that integrates real-time behavioural and neural monitoring within an ecologically valid, adaptive setting. The system enables systematic examination of human-rhythm synchronisation with either human or virtual AI partners under masked conditions, addressing the target of human-machine equivalence while simultaneously validating the suitability of portable EEG for capturing task-related neural dynamics. We first address overall system performance in relation to comparable in-house paradigms, followed by an evaluation of the study's primary targets.

4.1 System performance and behavioural outcomes

The system was designed to support wireless EEG acquisition, enabling unrestricted natural interaction. Although a single Ethernet cable was retained to ensure precise temporal alignment between EEG and stimulus streams, the framework successfully supported a stable, synchronised rhythmic interaction. Through reliable alignment and extraction of behavioural and neural markers, the system demonstrated its viability and supported the assessment of both study targets.

Participants achieved high synchronisation accuracy in simple conditions ($Med R = 0.88$), with substantially reduced performance in complex interactions ($Med R = 0.31$). These outcomes replicate prior benchmarks for simple tasks and exceed previously reported performance in complex conditions for the percentage of synchronised trials ($R > 0.05$, 38% vs. 24% in [16]). The improvement likely reflects the combined effects of pre-screening to inform participants, enhanced audio-visual realism, and the adaptive behaviour of the virtual AI agent. In particular, audio-visual embodiment of the partner may have strengthened engagement and entrainment [72]. Furthermore, replacing a fixed computer partner with an adaptive agent likely promoted synchrony [24], by more closely approximating corrective human behaviour. Given that musical sophistication scores were comparable to prior work (previous: $M = 24.8$, current: $M = 26.6$), these gains are attributed to design improvements rather than participant-related

differences, although non-considered subjective features may have contributed.

The paradigm's suitability is further supported by generally positive subjective ratings of pleasure and flow. Participants reported enjoyable interactions (median pleasure +50) and stable flow across partner types and task complexities. Stable flow suggests a well-calibrated balance between task demands and participant skill [56], while trial-by-trial variability in synchrony, pleasure, and arousal confirms that the framework elicits differentiated yet controlled affective responses.

The minimal motor requirement of finger tapping facilitates future extension and adaptability of the paradigm, ranging from full-body motion capture and musical performance to therapeutic applications. Its simplicity also enables use with populations with limited mobility, including individuals with Parkinson's disease or autism spectrum disorders. Building on prior gait-based and rhythm interventions [7], participants could engage in rhythmic interaction to support motor learning and rehabilitation, with embodied visual feedback potentially facilitating motor imagery and recovery [73]. Moreover, the accessibility of neural features within an active paradigm opens research avenues for EEG-driven closed-loop systems, enabling adaptive interactions tailored to individual behaviour or neural profiles in both medical and entertainment-based contexts. While these applications require empirical validation in future work, their potential is clearly supported by the present findings.

4.2 Neural modulations

The reduced eight-channel EEG montage reliably captured neural modulation signatures associated with rhythmic interaction, fulfilling the second target of the study and aligning with prior research. Spectral analyses revealed robust peaks at beat- and task-related frequencies across all interaction conditions, consistent with established patterns in rhythmic perception and motor entrainment [10, 12, 74, 75]. The presence of harmonic components further reflected the transient non-sinusoidal nature of evoked neural activity [76].

Beyond task-specific frequencies, a shared, condition-invariant sub-harmonic at 0.625 Hz was consistently

observed, likely primed by the initial audio-visual rhythm illustration and reflecting a six-beat metrical grouping. This component suggests imposed cognitive grouping strategies that structure rhythmic perception and facilitate beat alignment [12, 77], in agreement with earlier work. Additional peaks unrelated to the currently performed rhythm (e.g., 1.25 Hz in 3:3 and 1.875 Hz in [2 : 2]) may indicate carry-over perceptual effects from preceding trials, consistent with reported trial-history and memory influences on rhythmic processing [16, 78, 79]. The persistence of task-related, harmonic, and subharmonic components - even during complex or weakly synchronised trials - the robustness of the framework and its strong agreement with existing literature.

Importantly, no significant differences in neural modulation were observed between human-human and human-machine (AI) interactions, indicating that both partner types elicited comparable cortical responses. While this resemblance does not imply equivalence in subjective experience, it indicates the framework's capacity to emulate human-like rhythmic engagement at a neural level. These findings demonstrate that portable low-density EEG can reliably capture key neural markers of beat perception and interaction, consistent with results obtained using higher-density EEG systems. Similar to prior work in neural emotion analysis [80], the framework enables evaluation of interaction-driven neural modulations, albeit with reduced spatial resolution and head coverage.

4.3 Human-machine equivalence

Converging behavioural and neural evidence suggests that the adaptive virtual AI agent effectively reproduced the core dynamics of human-human rhythm interaction while remaining less sensitive to variability in partner proficiency. Participants reported comparable levels of pleasure, arousal, and flow across human and AI conditions, confirming effective masking of the artificial partner and sustained engagement equivalent to human interaction. Together, these results demonstrate clear similarities between human and virtual AI partners in shaping subjective experience, directly addressing the first target of the study. This extends prior work using fixed metronomic partners, which frequently reported reduced synchrony and altered experiential outcomes [16, 24]. The agent's adaptivity appears critical for fostering more natural,

reciprocal interaction and for narrowing the perceptual gap between human and machine partners.

In complex interactions, behavioural synchrony did not differ between partner types, suggesting a shared performance ceiling. Both human and virtual AI partners showed limited capacity to compensate for alignment errors when executing polyrhythms with less proficient individuals. Notably, pre-screening demonstrated that participants could perform complex rhythms under guidance, implying that additional steering or feedback may be required during unguided interaction to attain stable synchrony. These findings indicate that tailored individual support - beyond audio-visual feedback - may be necessary to enhance synchrony in complex conditions, irrespective of partner type.

Conversely, simple conditions showed a trend towards higher synchrony with the virtual AI partner, although this effect did not survive correction for multiple comparisons. A potential explanation for the increase emerges from post-hoc analyses of simple interactions of inter-beat interval variability, which revealed greater temporal variability in the AI-generated beats than in human partner beats. Such variability may have facilitated mutual adaptation or compensated for human timing errors. Alternatively, reduced synchrony in human-human interactions may reflect cognitive fatigue or reduced engagement during prolonged, low-demand tasks [81]. Importantly, these subtle differences in synchrony were not reflected in experience, underscoring that perceived interaction quality is co-modulated by variability in other human dynamics rather than timing accuracy alone.

Overall, AI-mediated interactions elicited emotional and behavioural responses comparable to those observed in human-human interaction. The adaptive virtual AI agent, therefore, constitutes a scalable, controllable, and ecologically valid platform for studying human-rhythm interaction, lowering dependence on musical proficiency while broadening applications to rehabilitation and entertainment. By integrating a controllable virtual partner with real-time neural monitoring, the framework bridges the gap between tightly controlled laboratory paradigms and naturalistic, music-based interactions.

5 Limitations and future work

Neural modulations in this study were interpreted primarily as spectral responses to rhythmic stimuli. Because no distinction was made between externally evoked and internally generated neural activity, the observed peaks are best understood as markers of general physical entrainment rather than cognitively controlled timing mechanisms, thereby limiting inferences about higher-level cognitive processes. In addition, the assumed equivalence between the constructed motor localiser based on three electrodes and full-cap independent component analyses requires further validation. Further work should assess the extent to which task-related features are preserved under channel reduction and exclude potential selection bias introduced by the reduced montage. Similarly, the observed neural equivalence between human and AI interactions is constrained by this methodological construction and should be corroborated using high-density EEG, including consideration of more-advanced task-related processes, such as beta-band timing modulation mechanisms [82].

For complex interaction conditions, the behavioural synchrony metric R may underestimate true coordination. Reduced synchrony values likely reflect occasional missed beats or shifts in the perceived first-beat onset, which misalign executed taps with their theoretical reference construction. Consequently, R values should be interpreted cautiously, and future analyses may benefit from a windowed approach to minimise this effect. This limitation likely extends to neural analyses, where missed beats or phase shifts may similarly attenuate spectral peaks and reduce apparent full-interaction patterns.

Despite the system's multimodal design, the current setup remains constrained in motion freedom, behavioural spontaneity, and action diversity, as the interaction was limited to finger tapping. These factors reduced alignment with real-world musical interaction [32, 72]. In addition, the avatar may still lack expressive embodiment, potentially leading to perceptual decoupling due to the absence of embodied co-regulation [83]. Furthermore, the polyrhythmic conditions may have exceeded an optimal challenge level, as the majority of participants struggled to perform them reliably, thereby limiting their representativeness of successful synchronised interaction. Future paradigms should therefore favour less complex yet still challenging rhythmic interactions, while advancing towards fully wireless, motion-inclusive, and

participant-centred designs. The existing adaptive agent and real-time neural tracking provide promising foundations for emotion-driven adaptation and interaction optimisation.

Finally, the masking of partner identity may have encouraged more human-like responses towards the virtual AI agent, potentially reducing vigilance for experiential differences [84, 85]. Such effects may limit the paradigm's sensitivity to subtle behavioural or emotional distinctions, which are nevertheless critical for the development of bias-aware and transparent adaptive agents.

6 Conclusion

This work introduced a multi-modal paradigm for evaluating rhythmic interaction that supports both human-human and human-machine engagement, while simultaneously capturing behavioural, experiential, and neural responses. Partner identity was effectively masked, as no robust partner-type differences emerged under the present design in reported flow, pleasure, and arousal between interaction types, demonstrating virtual AI agent's capacity to elicit human-like experiential responses. Moreover, the adaptive virtual AI agent achieved behavioural synchrony comparable to human partners, with indications of further alignment improvement, illustrating its potential for user-specific responsiveness and adaptive interaction.

The framework provides an ecologically valid, yet experimentally controllable environment for studying rhythmic interaction. It further enables time-aligned EEG acquisition and stimulus-locked neural modulation analysis using a lightweight and portable setup, with observed neural patterns closely matching those reported in the literature.

Collectively, these advancements support the development of future closed-loop interaction systems, in which real-time neural markers dynamically inform agent behaviour to optimise the user experience. With potential applications ranging from entertainment to rehabilitation, the proposed design lays the foundations for more immersive, adaptive, and emotionally attuned rhythmic paradigm technologies.

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8 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest of any kind in the presented work.

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A Appendix: Mixed-Effect model overview

To consider the separate contribution of both partner-type (PARTNER) and task complexity (COMPLEXITY), linear mixed-effects models evaluated their effects and interactions for each of the 4 considered experience metrics (Flow, Pleasure, Arousal, and Behavioural synchrony R). All models were fitted to 214 observations (no test-retest), treating participant ID as a random intercept (`statsmodels.formula.api()`).

	Coef.	Std.Err.	z	$P > z $	0.025	0.975
Intercept	22.730	0.707	32.166	0	21.345	24.115
PARTNER[AI]	0.361	0.721	0.501	0.617	-1.053	1.775
COMPLEXITY[Complex]	-0.639	0.729	-0.877	0.381	-2.068	0.789
PARTNER[AI] x COMPLEXITY[Complex]	0.033	1.020	0.032	0.974	-1.967	2.033

Table 2: Linear Mixed-effect model for experienced flow.

	Coef.	Std.Err.	z	$P > z $	0.025	0.975
Intercept	57.681	3.238	17.812	0.000	51.334	64.028
PARTNER[AI]	4.159	3.512	1.184	0.236	-2.724	11.041
COMPLEXITY[Complex]	-7.170	3.549	-2.020	0.043	-14.126	-0.214
PARTNER[AI] x COMPLEXITY[Complex]	1.592	4.968	0.320	0.749	-8.144	11.328

Table 3: Linear Mixed-effect model for experienced pleasure.

	Coef.	Std.Err.	z	$P > z $	0.025	0.975
Intercept	41.682	3.528	11.816	0.000	34.768	48.596
PARTNER[AI]	-2.492	3.255	-0.766	0.444	-8.872	3.887
COMPLEXITY[Complex]	7.082	3.289	2.153	0.031	0.635	13.529
PARTNER[AI] x COMPLEXITY[Simple]	2.233	4.603	0.485	0.628	-6.789	11.256

Table 4: Linear Mixed-effect model for experienced arousal.

	Coef.	Std.Err.	z	$P > z $	0.025	0.975
Intercept	0.793	0.036	22.247	0.000	0.723	0.863
PARTNER[AI]	0.077	0.042	1.845	0.065	-0.005	0.159
COMPLEXITY[Complex]	-0.396	0.042	-9.401	0.000	-0.478	-0.313
PARTNER[AI] x COMPLEXITY[Complex]	-0.032	0.059	-0.537	0.592	-0.147	0.084

Table 5: Linear Mixed-effect model for experienced behavioural synchrony R .

B Appendix: Resultant vector length distribution

To accommodate a proper measurement selection, where synchrony was attained, a two-step criterion was applied to the interactions. The distribution of relative phase angles (T_n vs B_n^*) per measurement was verified to be neither random nor uniform via a Rayleigh test ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, a minimal required resultant vector length $R = 0.5$ was selected. This value was based on previous work by *Moens et al.* identifying a transition from incoherent to coherent phase alignment in gait at $R = 0.74$, where individuals walked at a preferred pace while music played. This transition from random to properly aligned cadence inspired a similar threshold here, where a slightly lower threshold was based on the current study's transition regions from incoherent to coherent phase alignment in complex conditions $R = 0.5-0.65$, Figure 10.

Figure 10: Distribution of Resultant vector lengths R across measurements ($N = 214$), excluding test-retest cases. Transition regions between phase coherent and incoherent tapping were highlighted in grey.

C Appendix: Measurement selection overview

The initial 300 measurements (10 measurements for 30 participants) were removed based on present noise artefact or absent behavioural synchrony and summarised below in Table 6.

Condition	N_{noisy}	N_{sync}	$N_{sync,AI}$	$N_{sync,HP}$
[2 : 2]	53	52	27	25
[3 : 3]	102	102	48	54
[2 : 3]	54	22	12	10
[3 : 2]	53	19	12	7
[3 : 3] (no retest)	54	54	26	28

Table 6: Measurement counts after removal of noisy measurements N_{noisy} and removal of noisy+synchronised measurements N_{sync} and the subdivision into interactions with an AI agent $N_{sync,AI}$ or human participant $N_{sync,HP}$